

A micromechanical analysis of plastic deformation for short fiber reinforced metal matrix composites

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ABSTRACT

Elastoplastic deformation of aligned short fiber reinforced metal matrix composites is studied by using micromechanical model and finite element method. The fiber is assumed to be elastic and the matrix elasto-viscoplastic. Local elasto-plastic stress field of the unit cell in composite is investigated in order to understand the mechanism of inelastic deformation and interactions between fiber and surrounding matrix of short-fiber composite materials.

Key words: short-fibers, metal matrix, composites, elastoplasticity, micromechanics, finite element method

Introduction

With extending of application field of composite materials, the ductile matrix composites, such as metal matrix composites, are being developed for good mechanical and workable properties. The ductile metal matrix is currently reinforced by continuous fiber, short fiber (whisker) or particle. These reinforcements often can deform only elastically. When a large external load is applied, the composites will exhibit a elastoplastic behaviour due to nonlinearity of the matrix surrounding the elastic fibers.

Several works have been done for inelastic deformation of continuous fiber reinforced composites and particle reinforced composites⁽¹⁻⁴⁾. But the study of elastoplastic behaviour of short fiber or whisker reinforced metal matrix composites is very limited. In short fiber composites there are complex fiber-fiber and fiber-matrix interactions which influence the distribution of local field and overall properties. Therefore, it is important to investigate the microscopic elastoplastic deformation of short fiber compo-

sites in order to better understand the reinforcement mechanism of composites. Aboudi (1986) has proposed a continuum model to predict elastoplastic properties of short fiber composites where the matrix material is described by an internal variable theory. But this model can not give the local stress distribution. Agarwal (1974), Christman (1989) and Tvergaard (1990) have employed finite element method to investigate microplastic deformation. Advantage of using finite element method is that the geometry effects of the microstructure can be accounted for, and a detailed microscopic stress field can be given. However, These works are not concerned with the effect of interactions between fiber and matrix on elastoplastic behaviour of short fiber composites. In this paper, a micromechanical model and elastoplastic finite element method are used to investigate the microscopic deformation of short fiber reinforced metal matrix composites whose matrix material is characterized by Bodner-Partom's unified constitutive equations. We shall focus our attention on the mechanism of interactions be-

tween fiber and matrix in short fiber composites.

Micromechanical model

The fiber is transversely isotropic, and the stress-strain relations are given by Hook's law. The matrix is elasto-viscoplastic, the nonelastic strain rate is given by.

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \lambda s \quad (1)$$

where s is the deviatoric stress tensor and λ is a scalar parameter:

$$\lambda = D_0 \exp \left[- \left(\frac{z^2}{3J_2} \right)^{\frac{n+1}{2n}} \right] / J_2^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where J_2 is the second invariant of the deviatoric stress tensor, and z is state variable:

$$z = z_1 + (z_0 - z_1) \exp(-m w_p / z_0) \quad (3)$$

where z_0 , z_1 , m and D_0 , n are material constants and w_p is the plastic work.

Table 1 lists the material constants of Boron / Aluminum system given in reference (9). These constants will be used in subsequent calculations.

Table 1 material constants of B / Al

	E(GPa)	μ	$D_0(S^{-1})$	$z_0(MPa)$	$z_1(MPa)$	m	n
B	400	0.2	-	-	-	-	-
Al	72.5	0.33	10^4	100	190	70	10

In short fiber composites, the fiber may be distributed in several patterns. This paper assumes that the unidirectional fibers are arranged in the matrix in a regular array as shown in Fig.1. A smallest repeating unit cell is analyzed, as shown

Fig.1 microstructure of the aligned short fiber composite

in Fig.2. Let x aligne in the fiber direction. A perfect interface between fiber and matrix is assumed. For given fiber volume fraction and aspect ratio, the aspect ratio of the unit cell can be solitarily determined.

A prescribed displacement boundary condition is applied to the unit cell in the fiber axis.

$$\begin{aligned} u &= 0 \quad \text{in } x = 0 \\ u &= u_0 \quad \text{in } x = a, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

and the end effect of the unit cell will be accounted for in the Saint-Venant's sense.

Finite element analysis

A simple elastic mechanics finite element method in the fiber domain and elastic viscoplastic finite element method based on equation (1) in the matrix domain are established. The energy functional in term of stress rate and deformation rate is written as

$$\pi = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \dot{\sigma} \dot{\epsilon} dv - \int_A \dot{f} \dot{u} dA \quad (5)$$

where f is traction force vector.

The finite element form of equilibrium equation is that

$$K \dot{u} = \dot{F} + \dot{P} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} K &= \int_V B^T D B dv \\ \dot{F} &= \int_A N^T \dot{f} dA \\ \dot{P} &= \int_A B^T D \dot{\epsilon}^p dv \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Fig.2 unit cell

There are several integration strategies for solution of equation (6). Here the predictor-corrector method with automatic time step is adopted.

Local stress field

To better understand the load transfer mechanism of short fiber composites, we shall investigate the local stress distributions when the composites deform plastically. It is difficult to account for the fiber-matrix interactions and effect of fiber discontinuity on the local stress fields. We give the analysis of the example, Boron / Aluminum system, to illustrate this problem.

In the present analysis, the difference between elastic moduli of the fiber and the matrix is very great, so the discontinuity of fibers will effect only the local fields of the surrounding matrix. This is because the relatively compliant matrix can develop the plastic deformation to relax partly the stress concentration around the fiber ends.

Fig.3 and 4 show the normal stress distributions in the matrix for $\alpha=20$, $v_f=0.2$, where the average strain of unit cell is 0.5 and 1.0 percent. There are high stress domain in front of the fiber ends due to the fiber discontinuity. This high normal stress may result in easily debonding of interface between the fiber ends and matrix. When the plastic deformation increases, the high normal stress domain in matrix enlarges. Although there is high normal stress of the matrix in front of the fiber ends, the constraint of the adjoining fibers will not allow the large deformation of the matrix. It was accounted for in Agarwal's (1974) single fiber model through applying specified displacement boundary conditions in the unit cell.

Fig.5 and 6 show the shear stress distributions in the matrix at different strain levels for $\alpha=20$, $v_f=0.2$. The shear stress of the matrix varies quickly near the fiber ends due to the material discontinuity. A largest shear stress reaches at the

longitudinal interface between the fiber and matrix near the fiber ends. The shear stress is transferred from matrix to fiber through the interface. The fiber normal stress consists of the shear stress through the longitudinal interface and the normal stress through the fiber end interfaces from matrix. Since the longitudinal surface area of the fiber is much greater than the cross section area for thin fibers, the primary load transfer into the fiber is through the interfacial shear stress. The plastic deformation of the matrix will appear in the high stress domains firstly, and make the load transfer efficient in these domains decrease.

Conclusions

There are complex interactions between the fiber and matrix in short fiber composites. This paper gives the analysis for effect of the fiber discontinuity on the stress distributions of the surrounding matrix in the B / Al composite under elastic-plastic deformation. Present method can be used to study the stress field in the fiber and at the interface, also to predict the elastoplastic properties of short fiber composites.

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Fig.3 matrix normal stress contours for strain level 0.5%

Fig.4 matrix normal stress contours for strain level 1.0%

Fig.5 matrix shear stress contours for strain level 0.5%

Fig.6 matrix shear stress contours for strain level 1.0%